

Digital Metamorphosis - Impact of technology in disrupting the business landscape

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Abstract:- A modern phenomena called "digital transformation" is forcing companies to rethink their core business processes and adopt new business models. Since it would provide them with a methodical and organized manner to manage change inside the organization from all perspectives and levels, enterprise architects need an enterprise modelling framework for this. This paper describes the traits of digital transformation that were discovered during this review. This article describes the aspects of digital transformation that were discovered via this review. Enterprise architects can now model and evaluate developing businesses thanks to a framework for the future that was developed by taking characteristics from digital technology. Enterprise architects would be able to evaluate firms going through digital transformation while taking stakeholder goals and motivations, as well as the complexity of developing software systems and business processes, into consideration with the use of such a modelling framework.

Keywords—Enterprise architecture, enterprise modelling, digital transformation, and requirements engineering are some related terms.

I. Introduction

Businesses have been able to alter and achieve a range of goals thanks to recent improvements in software and related digital technologies. A popular phrase nowadays is "digital transformation," which entails altering a company's fundamental business processes via the use of cutting-edge digital technology [2].

The enterprise's processes for producing its goods and services, as well as the broader organisational structure, are all impacted by digital transformation [7]. Businesses are replacing or augmenting traditional business models by developing disruptive digital models employing cutting-edge technology and software [1]. In many different industries, software is becoming a crucial facilitator of expanding corporate capabilities and possibilities [3]. Software-induced changes may be introduced gradually or abruptly, depending on the circumstances or goals of the organization.

Corporate architecture (EA) is essential for building corporate software and technology systems while taking the business context and environment into account [11]. EA assists in simulating and analyzing multiple-perspective changes brought on by technological and software improvements [12]. Recent developments in ArchiMate—such as the Motivation extension, strategy, and physical layers—highlight the necessity of taking several perspectives into account in complicated contexts like those of digital transformation [4]. Enterprise architects can now negotiate the difficulties of digital transformation and adjust to changing business contexts thanks to these developments.

Numerous detailed literature reviews have been carried out [6] in an effort to better define and understand the digital shift. In our work, we also perform a thorough literature analysis, but our aim was to pinpoint the fundamental characteristics as opposed to defining the notion of digital transformation [8]. By observing behavioral patterns in numerous firms going through digital transformation, several characteristics may be found.

II. Literature Review

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The author [1] in his paper focused on adaptive enterprise architecture. He discussed about the intense pressure, increasing shareholder prices, etc. He mentioned how IT needs to become business saviour for them.

The author [2] proposed research on the nine elements of digital transformation. They took interviews of 157 executives of big companies and based upon those interviews, gave their theory in the paper.

The author [3] proposes a relational theory of identity to explore the implications of digital disruption on organizational identity. It highlights the need for Information Systems research to investigate the reasons behind the disruption caused by digital technologies.

The author [4] discusses the 103 organizational case studies that are used to propose a typology of digital transformation from the standpoint of change management.

The author [5] discusses how in order to modernize the automotive industry and cities, the text emphasizes the necessity of cooperation between lawmakers, local governments, and manufacturers to build a digital and data-driven infrastructure for multi-modal smart cities.

The author [6] investigates digital disruption, a phrase for the flawed value logics that have been embedded in digital ecosystems as a result of technical progress.

The author [7] discusses the impact of COVID-19 on the fashion retail industry in the Gulf Cooperation Council (GCC) countries and suggests that fashion retailers need to adopt digitalization technologies and an adaptive supply chain to survive in the post-pandemic business environment.

The author [8] addresses the adoption of digital transformation in the banking sector, highlighting disruptive technologies as social media, mobile, big data, cloud computing, internet of things, artificial intelligence, fin-tech, blockchain, virtual reality, and augmented reality.

The author [9] in his paper how in order to gain theoretical understanding of how the demand environment affects the competitive dynamics in technological rivalry, the study introduces preference overlap and preference symmetry as novel constructs in demand conditions.

The author [10] discusses how in addition to decentralized storage, blockchain technology can provide novel financial and investment strategies.

The author [11] analyses how technology helps consumers in the e-hailing scenario to recognize, engage with, and transpose. Furthermore, it reveals the types of motivating affordances used by innovative platforms and technologies.

The author [12] reviews the contamination routes and degradation of Bisphenol A (BPA) in the aquatic environment and its endocrine-disruptive effects on aquatic organisms.

III. Methodology

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A comprehensive literature search was carried out using the step review methodology for information systems research provided in the model [8]. The study begins by outlining the characteristics of digital transformation for corporate architects and researchers in order to frame the issue [9]. We planned to provide explicit specifications for an enterprise modelling approach with the aid of these characteristics in order to model and analyses how firms are evolving as a result of new digital technologies [10]. A protocol or training manual weren't necessary because there was only one reviewer working on the review.

It began by identifying all the papers that met an inclusion criterion and contained the terms "digital transformation [13]. We decided to restrict our search to just digital transformation even though other terms (like "Digital Strategy," "Enterprise Digitization," etc.) might be thought as a workable substitute. In order to exclude works that used an older or different meaning of the term, the search was restricted to journal articles and conference papers on digital transformation that were published between 2010 and 2019.

Fig. 1. The order of particular articles by year.

The author [10] discusses how in addition to decentralized storage, blockchain technology can provide novel financial and investment strategies

It checked the titles and abstracts of the 698 papers during the screening process to see if any of them made an effort to characterize the properties, traits, or adoption issues of the digital transformation [15]. Many questions were explicitly taken into account during this stage of the review process such as what are traditional and digital business model, their qualities, forces for adoption, difficulties, etc. Effort was made to establish theme topics that might be used to group the discussion points throughout these papers because the digital transformation trend has a broad impact and scope. The talk was organized into thematic parts to highlight reoccurring topics and trends. Through a qualitative examination of the reasons for each of the topic categories, we were able to isolate eight distinct aspects of the digital transition that were present across our complete final data set.

Fig. 2. Article distribution based on attributes. The overall number of articles surpasses 36 because one item may have numerous characteristics.

Here it's outlined, the methodical methodology used for a literature review for independent replication by other researchers [14]. We do acknowledge that the review made use of qualitative analysis and reasoning. Other reviewers using a similar review method could theoretically arrive at somewhat different conclusions. or discovered other traits.

IV. Definitions Associated with The Digital Transformation of Enterprises

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Eight specific traits were found as a result of the literature review process. Based on recurring themes in the papers in the final dataset, a narrative for each is given below. The list of features is not exhaustive nor definitive because the identification process relies on qualitative reasoning and might be biased by the observer.

1. Business Models and Strategies

Enterprises use business strategies and business models to create and preserve competitive advantages in a changing

environment. Improved enterprise performance is made possible by operational processes and business strategy alignment. Business and technological processes for enterprises must support enterprise strategies and be coordinated, created, and tailored accordingly. Technology-driven difficulties may be improved and processes can be made more efficient by fostering strong business-software development linkages, employing agile requirements engineering methodologies, and integrating innovation in business models with changes in strategy.

Fig. 3. Evolution of the digital newspaper.

2. Business Agility

Businesses that are experiencing digital transformation are constantly adapting to external conditions, rising rivalry, and the entry of new players from non-traditional industries. Similarly, Both the software system that has been established and the software processes used to create such systems can benefit from such improvements. Collectively, such a strategy would enable businesses to increase their responsiveness and agility.

3. Focus on the customer

Businesses attempt to provide a consistently improved client experience by focusing more on their needs. The goods and services they provide. Software development processes may be moved closer to users, providing greater client consideration during the design, development, delivery, and operation phases, allowing businesses to react swiftly to shifting consumer demands and market trends.

4. Delivering Products and Solutions in Rapid Cycle

Rapid delivery cycles for goods and services should be adopted by businesses to cut down on time, improve customer focus, address operational and support concerns, and show a higher level of response to shifting internal and external situations. This method shortens the time it takes to launch new features and goods, resulting in a method that is both more effective and customer-focused.

5. Organizations with Multiple Speeds

Businesses engaged in digital transformation have distinctive cultures, practices, methodologies, software tools, and surroundings that necessitate solutions that are specifically designed for their regional context. This is especially true in organisations that operate on two speeds, where one side is better able to respond to customer needs because it is "decoupled" from the other, which houses outdated technology (and the processes that go along with them). Organizational structures, separate technologies, software systems, and distinct business processes are just a few of the strategies used to accomplish separation, which ensures successful communication and cooperation.

6. Making Data-Driven Decisions

Technology advancements in big data are making it possible to acquire, store, and process vast amounts of data. Enterprise data are used in decision-making to gradually improve operational procedures, strategic decisions, product design, etc., among other domains. This business feed-back and feedforward loops are being used more and more by software engineering methodologies as well to aid in better decision-making for the design of software processes and software systems.

7. Organisational and Social Aspects

These organisational changes must be thoughtfully and methodically considered while taking into account changes to business operations, technology, and software systems. Creating and understanding these intricate connections while taking into account issues with corporate architecture and design as well as other business aspects like culture, context, and alignment is tough. When designing and integrating software and technology, social and organizational variables are frequently overlooked in favor of process activity. Understanding why is essential to identifying complicated issues, such as the connections between people, businesses, and procedures.

8. Automating business processes

Businesses are investing more money in business process automation to speed up execution, lower costs, and increase process efficiency.

Digitalization	
Benefits	Challenges
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Imperative for Business Survival • Seamless Customer Experience • Increased Productivity • Responsive Supply Chains • Data Analytics and customer personalization • Enabler - Multiple optimization tools like AI, ML, and DC automation 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Change Management & transformation Failure • Employee Uncertainty • Data Integrity across multiple systems • Burden of Legacy Systems • Culture Change • Security – Internal & Customer Facing • Project Execution Failure

Fig. 4. Benefits and challenges of digitalization.

Automation, however, has some complications that must be balanced against the benefits that are thought to be gained. Shorter release cycles and quicker feature delivery are made possible by automation, which has a substantial influence on software development and delivery.

V. Modeling Framework Requirements

It is possible to abstract out the various traits influencing enterprise digital transformation as a collection of specifications for a modelling framework. By examining each attribute in light of its implications for the business on a process, software artefact, data, and social level, these needs were determined.

1. Connections Between Processes

Organizations rely on a variety of processes, such as planning, design, operational, and transaction procedures, for their existence and success. These processes happen for variable lengths of time and with varying regularity. The text describes the steps in the process and how they work together.

- How may the linkages and associations between various business, technological, and software processes be represented visually?
- What effects do modifications to the process architecture for achieving particular corporate business objectives have on the architecture?

2. Various Process Types and Levels

Process architectures can contain a variety of levels of process dynamics since they encompass a number of distinct processes. The border transitions (between various process levels) are not totally obvious to the casual observer, nor are these numerous levels of dynamics. As a result, a process architecture would need to include information and characteristics that would make it possible to recognize and distinguish between distinct process segment types and levels. All process segments within these types and levels would have a common set of characteristics and behavior that would be defined by the boundaries of the processes. Any process' component operations could be shifted across level borders, but doing so would have ramifications that must be understood.

3. Goals for the Organization and Process

Any effort to restructure an organization's business and technology processes must respect any functional goals that have previously been established while also taking organizational priorities into consideration when weighing trade-offs between non-functional goals. Goal-modeling strategies assist in expressing, contrasting, and assessing the configurations of commercial, technical, and software processes. Functional requirements (FRs) or non-functional requirements (NFRs) can be used to classify these objectives. It is possible to identify process architectures that cooperate to accomplish a common objective by integrating enterprise and process goal-oriented viewpoints. Analyses are made easier by how the process architecture relates to established goals.

4. Trade-Off Analysis

Technology-enabled innovation introduction must now be viewed from a variety of angles because it can no longer be assumed to have only limited effects. There are frequently numerous possible reconfigurations of the process architecture, but these potential options must be verified in light of other factors, such as the data's accessibility, the participants' prioritizations, the implications for the complexity of the system, and any effects on business goals and objectives. To take into account the effects of and on multiple systems-, enterprise-, process-, and social-level factors, trade-off analysis would need to be done. Thus, analyzing and choosing amongst different process architectural configurations (together with the design and use of supporting software tools) can be done by gauging how well objectives are met. Some of the most current advancements and methods in software engineering place an emphasis on multi-dimensional viewpoints by taking into account organizational structure, company culture, software design, development, and deployment processes.

- Can questions like the following be posed? • Would reconfigurations to process architecture require a change in roles and responsibilities? How might these trade-offs be assessed?

5. Design of Abstract Software Artefacts

If you want your software to be flexible and adaptable, take into account how business processes and software artefacts interact. As a result, activities function more smoothly and run-time decision-making is facilitated. Additionally, procedures that are in charge of creating software artefacts might employ software as a tool. software design artefacts in great detail employing modelling methods like UML diagrams, which enable exact software development and implementation. However, it is vital to comprehend abstract differences in order to conceptually and visually analyze the software's involvement in and contribution to the broader corporate business and technological processes, particularly those that require change to introduce change.

6. Moving Design Choices Downstream

There are two degrees of processes: creating a tool or capacity and continuously consuming it. Depending on the activities that will occur downstream, several designs and methods could be developed. Some design choices could be put off until runtime or use-time in order to ensure flexible use. As a result, there are numerous options for determining how much designing should be done before an artefact may be utilized by a human user or as part of a process. Complete designing, where design decisions are made while the artefact is being used, gives consumers the greatest amount of freedom. With this method, sophisticated design is not necessary, and decision-making is made possible with greater flexibility. Complex trade-offs would accompany each alternative. Software tools and artefacts can be created to build permanent capabilities that can be continuously (re)used by people without them being aware of how the capability was created. The following inquiries are made possible by such differences in design-use process configuration:

- Should some actions or choices be put off until closer to the time of use in order to benefit from data that is nearly real-time and foster flexibility in the use of the artefact?

7. Deferred versus upfront planning

The necessary process activities are often specified by process modelling approaches (like BPMN), but not their selection or planning. Such a factor should be considered by businesses going

Post COVID-19 Business Strategy for Fashion Retailers in GCC				
Digitalization	Leveraging Social Media	Adaptive Supply Chains	Omnichannel Fulfilment Models	Sustainability
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Fortify Digital Competencies • Digital Gateway to the Consumer • Digital enabled Value Chains 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Interconnectedness to the community • Hyperconnectivity • Age of social influencers 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Agile, Flexible, Networked • Regional, Integrated, Local and Highly Responsive • Focused more on availability rather than cost 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Multiple, interchangeable Fulfilment Models • Channel Agnostic Fulfilment • Faster and cheaper fulfilment ecosystem 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Social Responsibility • Environment Friendly Fashion • Movement against extreme consumerism

Fig. 5. Post-pandemic business strategies

through change. Various plans (and the procedures that go along with them) may be created depending on how the downstream process activities will carry out the plans. Due to stale data, obsolete analytics, or flexibility in process or system design, plan-related operations may be delayed. As a result, there is some degree of planning that can be done to affect how downstream process activities behave and are carried out. Run-time/execution time decisions are made regarding process execution. Alternatives for the process configuration would need to be carefully weighed in light of potential trade-offs. The following queries can be addressed depending on whether the processes are being planned for or being carried out.

For transformative operations, businesses must monitor and respond to changing conditions, employing sense-and-response loops to continually adapt and advance. Processes in business and technology that operate at various degrees of dynamics and timelines sense and react. As an illustration, the sensing component may occur on a machine timeframe (using automated data-driven systems) while the acting component occurs on a human timescale (using management decision-making). The enterprise would ascertain the reason and requirement for change during the sensing phase. The business would choose the best change options at the reacting stage.

It is necessary to design out these feedback and feedforward pathways in the process architecture and tag them with process activities. These methods would make possible.

- Illustrating the interactions that linear lines or cyclic loops may have with other paths or objects while illustrating their presence in any enterprise.
 - Illustrating the numerous timelines that a loop crosses and the effects on the process level when these loops are rearranged or process activities are moved across different timeframes inside the loop itself.
8. Speed, timeframes, and process cycles should be shown and explained.

Automation, enhanced productivity, improved release cadence, and other increased organizational benefits are possible because to software-enabled enterprise innovation and transformation. Different strategies might need to be used in various environments. These, however, frequently come at the expense of other enterprise concerns, such as an increase in solution complexity, higher cost, decreased flexibility, resistance to adoption, etc. Sometimes there are internal variances, where the software artefact specifies the appropriate delivery speed. It is necessary to depict the process cycles in a way that would enable potential reconfigurations to increase execution frequency and adapt the activities involved in process execution. Businesses must be aware of issues like these.

- How might process activities be represented and rearranged to give clients faster software development and release cycles?
- Which of the several above-mentioned options is the most effective strategy for enhancing delivery cadence? How do you decide which is best?

9. Social Actors

The goals of any innovation exercise may be supported or opposed by various actors, and any company change may favorably or unfavorably collide with their personal interests. Additionally, actors can participate in cycles of sense-and-response and have roles at various process levels as software processes or software artefacts develop, their duties and roles may also change. This might also be reciprocal, with software modifications taking place as player influences and role dynamics alter. Actor and process are the two perspectives.

- Knowledge of potential modifications to roles and responsibilities brought on by process reorganization.
- Determining whether organizational divisions and hierarchies are aligned with the signed and accountable processes, or whether they are not.

VI. Conclusions

The purpose of this article is to provide business architects with instructions for building an enterprise modelling framework to help them comprehend the changes brought about by software advancements and digital technologies. The framework addresses systemic, business, procedural, and societal problems while highlighting systemic, enterprise, process, and social-level difficulties encountered by organizations in response to digital transformation.

In order to better identify and categories papers that are relevant to businesses going through cycles of software-enabled change, we intend to enhance the criteria of the systematic literature review in future work. This, in turn, should assist corroborate our current findings, supply additional material for examination, and make it possible to identify new requirements. During continual, incremental transformation, architects may examine enterprises from a variety of angles using a framework for enterprise modelling.

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